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Evaluation of Groundwater Potential Using Integrated Geophysical Data in Parts of Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Southern Nigeria

C. Amos-Uhegbu^{1*}, M. U. Igboekwe¹, K. T. Eke² and U. K. Eme¹

¹Department of Physics (Geophysics), College of Physical and Applied Sciences, Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, P.M.B. 7267 Umuahia, Abia-State, Nigeria.

²Department of Physics and Electronics, Abia State Polytechnic, Aba, P.M.B. 7166 Aba, Abia-State, Nigeria.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. Author MUI designed the study, while all the authors were actively involved in the field investigations. Author CAU wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Authors MUI and CAU managed the analyses of the study. Authors CAU, UKE and KTE managed the literature searches. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

This study was carried out to investigate the groundwater potential in Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike area of Abia State, Nigeria. A total of nine vertical electrical soundings were acquired and the results were correlated with records available from an existing well together with previous lithologic deductions. A range of 4 to 6 geoelectric layers was delineated in this study; though the fourth and fifth geoelectric layers were predominant. Results showed that the aquifer is located within the third layers for the 4-layered zone and the fifth and sixth layers for the other layered zones. The depth to the shallowest aquifer is about 30m at VES 4 with the aquifer resistivity of 13124Ωm and transmissivity of 258.6 m²/d. The area has huge groundwater potentials with the best prospects at VES 2 and less promising results at VES 5.

*Corresponding author: E-mail: nenyemos@yahoo.com;

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1. INTRODUCTION

Water beneath the ground surface in soil pore spaces and in the fractures of rock formations is usually referred to as groundwater.

Groundwater is a natural resource with its characteristics being greatly determined by the geologic properties of the host rock.

A porous substratum that is able to hold and yield (transmit) an appreciable quantity of groundwater is called an aquifer.

Thus, groundwater acquisition is mainly dependent on the reliable empirical knowledge of the geology of the area and the depth of aquifer.

1.1 Location and Geology and Hydrology of the Study Area

The study area (Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike) lies within latitudes 5°28'

and 5°29' N and longitudes 7°32' and 7°33'E, and has characteristic annual average temperature ranges of about 29°– 31°C. The area falls within the sub-equatorial belt with relative humidity values over 70%; while the wet season spans from Mid-April to October with rainfall peaks in July and September and a short break in August.

There are about 11 different geologic formations in Abia State of Nigeria but the Benin Formation of the Cenozoic Niger Delta covers almost half of the entire state.

Geologically, the study area Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike (MOUUA) is situated in the Benin Formation of the Cenozoic Niger-Delta basin of Nigeria (Fig. 1). The area is part of the oldest surface outcrop of the Cenozoic eastern Niger-Delta basin because it is situated immediately after the Bende-Ameki Formation of the Anambra basin.

Fig. 1. Geologic map of Abia State showing the Local Government Areas and the study area (Modified after Geological Survey of Nigeria (GSN), 1985)

1.2 Significance of the Study and Choice of Method

Industrialization and urbanization, together with increase in population and rising standards of living usually add pressure on natural resources [1].

The presence of National Root Crop Research Institute (NRCRI), Umudike; the Umuahia Campus of Abia State University (ABSUPAC) and Government College Umuahia (GCU) have also added to an increase in the population of the area (Fig. 2).

The preference of groundwater to surface water by the teeming population; together with the collapse of the municipal water supply has made

groundwater the main source of water supply for almost every sector in the area [2,3].

Since groundwater plays a major role in meeting the ever increasing demands for various purposes in the area; therefore, an overview of the groundwater potential of the area is essential for effective exploitation and management.

For a large scale development of groundwater, a reliable estimate of groundwater potential is essential [4]. This is usually actualized with well outlined techniques using modern scientific tools. Many approaches and methods have been used in the search for groundwater.

Geophysical surveys are most widely used because of the basic advantage of providing more accurate results than other methods.

Fig. 2. Map of Ikwuano-Umuahia area showing the study area

Valuable information with respect to distribution, thickness, and depth of groundwater bearing formation can be provided by geophysical methods.

Many geophysical techniques have been used in groundwater exploration [5,6,7]; but the most widely used is the electrical resistivity method [8,9,10]. This is because less field manpower is required and the equipment is portable; hence the field operation is easy. It also has greater depth of penetration thus clarifying the subsurface structure together with the delineation of the groundwater.

For the fact that groundwater accumulates in sedimentary rocks (sands, gravels, silt, limestone etc), and also in denature crystalline basement rocks (weathered overburden, joints, fractures and faults zones). The electrical resistivity method can be best employed to estimate the thickness of overburden and also the thickness of weathered layer.

The determination of the electrical resistivity of subsurface materials (rocks, minerals etc.) can be realized using the subsurface resistivity distribution to the ground. This is at times related to the physical conditions of interest (lithology, porosity, degree of water saturation and presence or absence of voids in the rocks).

In areas where good electrical resistivity contrast exists between the water bearing formation and the underlying rocks, electrical resistivity methods are effectively used for groundwater exploration [11]. This method enables the determination of the electrical resistivity of the subsurface by sending an electric current into the ground and simultaneously measuring the electrical potential produced by the current.

The Vertical Electrical Soundings (VES) technique of electrical resistivity method gives detailed information of vertical succession of individual thicknesses, resistivities and their different conducting zones; therefore it was chosen for this study.

Well documented in standard text books are the theories of both the electrical resistivity surveying method and the Schlumberger electrode configuration.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A total of nine Vertical Electrical Soundings (VES) were acquired using the Schlumberger

electrode configuration with two current electrodes 'AB/2' widely spaced out and two potential electrodes 'MN/2' closely spaced in between the current electrodes all along the survey line.

The current electrode spacing 'AB/2' was varied from 1.5 m to a maximum of 320 m; while the potential electrode spacing 'MN/2' was varied from 0.5 m to a maximum of 55 m.

The study area was transformed into a regular grid where nine nodal points were chosen as sounding stations at intervals of 250m. Out of the nine sounding stations, two were carried out in proximity to an existing borehole that has an available lithologic data (Fig. 3).

Garmin GPS 72 was used in determining the coordinates (longitude, latitude and elevation height above mean sea level) of each sounding point; and the ABEM Terrameter SAS 4000 was used in the data acquisition.

A 12V direct current (DC) from a battery was fed into the terrameter which was subsequently passed into the ground through the current electrodes 'AB/2' linked by insulated cables. The resultant potential difference (voltage) was determined using the potential electrodes 'MN/2'.

The observed field data is read off directly from the terrameter, and it is the ratio of the voltage to the current which is a measure of resistance of the subsurface (ground resistance). This measured ground resistance in ohms is used to compute the corresponding apparent resistivity in Ohm-meters by multiplying with the geometric factor.

The value of the geometric factor is a function of electrode spacing, thus giving the required apparent resistivity results as functions of depths of individual layers:

$$\rho_a = \pi R \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2}{2b} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where

ρ_a = Apparent resistivity.

a = 'AB/2' = Half current electrode spacing(m).

b = MN/2 = Half potential electrode spacing (m).

R = Resistance in ohms.

$\pi \left(\frac{a^2 - b^2}{2b} \right)$ = Geometric factor (K).

For each sounding point, the subsurface stratigraphy was delineated based on apparent resistivity differences. The apparent resistivity

values were plotted against current electrode spacing 'AB/2' on a log-log graph paper to obtain sounding curves. Subsequently, initial estimates of the resistivities and thicknesses of the various geoelectric layers were obtained and used for computer iteration using RESIST software package.

Q,A,K and H are used singly or in combination to indicate the variation of resistivity with depth (Fig. 4).

The resistivity type curves of the study area are indicative of good groundwater potential though based on the extent and the depth of probe of the survey, the groundwater potential of VES 4 and VES 5 are far less than those of VES 2 and VES 3. Some of the resistivity type curves are as shown (Figs. 5, 6 and 7).

A summary of the interpreted data which is within the limit of the probe is as shown in Table 1. This has revealed the existence of four to six geoelectric layers. The topsoil which is the first geoelectric layer has the resistivity varying from 13 Ω m to 4340 Ω m with thickness varying from 0.5 m to 1.4 m. The resistivity of the aquiferous zones varied from 611 Ω m at VES 2 to 99500 Ω m at VES 1. Amos-Uhegbu et al. [12] extensively worked within the study area and lithologically deduced from drill-hole and geoelectric data that sediments with resistivity < 100 Ω m are clays, 100 Ω m – 500 Ω m are silts, 500 Ω m – 1500 Ω m are fine-grained sands, 1500 Ω m – 3000 Ω m are medium-grained sands, 3000 Ω m – 5500 Ω m are coarse-grained sands, and > 5500 Ω m as sandstone [12]. This deduction has been used in the characterization of the various geoelectric layers. There is a likelihood of an existence of a possible shallow confined aquifer at VES 4 while the most reliable point recommended for sustainable groundwater potential is VES 2 (Fig. 8).

Using the hydraulic conductivity of 8.62 m/d established in the area through geostatistical approach of Amos-Uhegbu, [13], the highest aquifer transmissivity of the study area is that of VES 2 which is 810.28 m²/d.

Fig. 3. Data acquisition grid of the study area

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Sounding curve acquired over a horizontally stratified medium is a function of the resistivities and thicknesses of the layers together with the electrode configuration. When the calculated apparent resistivity is plotted against the corresponding half current electrode spacing (AB/2), VES curves are derived, and the letters

Fig. 4. Diagrammatic illustration of resistivity type curves for layered structures

Fig. 5. Typical vertical electrical sounding curve of VES 2 (University gate)

Fig. 6. Typical vertical electrical sounding curve of VES 1(School gate)

Fig. 7. Typical vertical electrical sounding curve of VES 4 (Stadium junction)

Fig. 8. A correlation of VES 2, VES 3 and a nearby borehole behind the Administrative building
(Source of borehole data [14])

Table 1. A profile of VES data and location points; with some calculated geo-electrical parameters

VES station	Location	GPS reading		Number of layers	Resistivity of layers (Ωm)	Thickness of layers (m)	Maximum depth of layers (m)	Layer conductivity σ	Fitting error (%)	Layer characteristics	Type curves
		Elevation (m) m.s.l	Latitude ($^{\circ}\text{N}$) Longitude ($^{\circ}\text{E}$)								
1	Opposite MOUUAU School gate	120.0 m	5° 28. 985 ¹ ° N 7° 32. 709 ¹ ° E	5	$\rho_1 = 88$ $\rho_2 = 2355$ $\rho_3 = 430$ $\rho_4 = 7280$ $\rho_5 = 99500$	$t_1 = 0.7$ $t_2 = 3.1$ $t_3 = 7.5$ $t_4 = 18$	$h_1 = 0.7$ $h_2 = 3.8$ $h_3 = 11.3$ $h_4 = 29.3$	$\sigma_1 = 0.011364$ $\sigma_2 = 0.000425$ $\sigma_3 = 0.002326$ $\sigma_4 = 0.000137$ $\sigma_5 = 0.000010$	10	L ₁ = Clay L ₂ = Medium-grained sands L ₃ = Silts L ₄ = Sandstone (Capillary fringe zone) L ₅ = Sandstone (Aquiferous zone)	KHA
2	Opposite MOUUAU University gate	129.5 m	5° 28. 826 ¹ ° N 7° 32. 765 ¹ ° E	6	$\rho_1 = 4340$ $\rho_2 = 3250$ $\rho_3 = 384$ $\rho_4 = 30200$ $\rho_5 = 611$ $\rho_6 = 5380$	$t_1 = 1.1$ $t_2 = 1.7$ $t_3 = 4.1$ $t_4 = 20.3$ $t_5 = 94.0$	$h_1 = 1.1$ $h_2 = 2.8$ $h_3 = 6.9$ $h_4 = 27.2$ $h_5 = 121.2$	$\sigma_1 = 0.000304$ $\sigma_2 = 0.000308$ $\sigma_3 = 0.002604$ $\sigma_4 = 0.000033$ $\sigma_5 = 0.001637$ $\sigma_6 = 0.000186$	8	L ₁ = Coarse-grained sands L ₂ = Coarse-grained sands L ₃ = Silts L ₄ = Sandstone (Capillary fringe zone) L ₅ = Fine-grained sands (Aquiferous zone) L ₆ = Coarse-grained sands (Aquiferous zone)	QHKH
3	Automobile Workshop	136.9 m	5° 28. 723 ¹ ° N 7° 32. 782 ¹ ° E	5	$\rho_1 = 13$ $\rho_2 = 15$ $\rho_3 = 85600$ $\rho_4 = 1345$ $\rho_5 = 2170$	$t_1 = 1.1$ $t_2 = 2.1$ $t_3 = 37.5$ $t_4 = 48$	$h_1 = 1.1$ $h_2 = 3.2$ $h_3 = 40.7$ $h_4 = 88.7$	$\sigma_1 = 0.076923$ $\sigma_2 = 0.066667$ $\sigma_3 = 0.000012$ $\sigma_4 = 0.000743$ $\sigma_5 = 0.000461$	12	L ₁ = Clay L ₂ = Clay L ₃ = Sandstone (Capillary fringe zone) L ₄ = Fine-grained sands (Aquiferous zone) L ₅ = Medium-grained sands (Aquiferous zone)	AKH
4	MOUUAU Stadium junction	115.5m	5° 28. 576 ¹ ° N 7° 32. 507 ¹ ° E	4	$\rho_1 = 184$ $\rho_2 = 78$ $\rho_3 = 13124$ $\rho_4 = 280.3$	$t_1 = 1.2$ $t_2 = 2.7$ $t_3 = 30.0$	$h_1 = 1.2$ $h_2 = 3.9$ $h_3 = 33.9$	$\sigma_1 = 0.005435$ $\sigma_2 = 0.012821$ $\sigma_3 = 0.000076$ $\sigma_4 = 0.003568$	10	L ₁ = Silts L ₂ = Clay L ₃ = Sandstone (Shallow Aquiferous zone) L ₄ = Silts	HK
5	Male Hostel junction	111.6 m	5° 28. 790 ¹ ° N 7° 32. 538 ¹ ° E	4	$\rho_1 = 84$ $\rho_2 = 10$ $\rho_3 = 1120.1$ $\rho_4 = 168.3$	$t_1 = 1.0$ $t_2 = 2.5$ $t_3 = 7.0$	$h_1 = 1.0$ $h_2 = 3.5$ $h_3 = 10.5$	$\sigma_1 = 0.011905$ $\sigma_2 = 0.1$ $\sigma_3 = 0.000893$ $\sigma_4 = 0.005942$	2.0	L ₁ = Clay L ₂ = Clay L ₃ = Fine-grained sands L ₄ = Silts	HK
6	MOUUAU ICT centre	121.4 m	5° 28. 925 ¹ ° N 7° 32. 553 ¹ ° E	6	$\rho_1 = 3800$ $\rho_2 = 65$ $\rho_3 = 667$ $\rho_4 = 50$ $\rho_5 = 3250$ $\rho_6 = 61800$	$t_1 = 0.5$ $t_2 = 0.7$ $t_3 = 2.2$ $t_4 = 7.0$ $t_5 = 12.6$	$h_1 = 0.5$ $h_2 = 1.2$ $h_3 = 3.4$ $h_4 = 10.4$ $h_5 = 23.0$	$\sigma_1 = 0.000263$ $\sigma_2 = 0.015385$ $\sigma_3 = 0.001499$ $\sigma_4 = 0.020000$ $\sigma_5 = 0.003077$ $\sigma_6 = 0.000016$	20	L ₁ = Coarse-grained sands L ₂ = Clay L ₃ = Fine-grained sands L ₄ = Clay L ₅ = Coarse-grained sands (Capillary fringe zone) L ₆ = Sandstone (Aquiferous zone)	HKHA

VES station	Location	GPS reading		Number of layers	Resistivity of layers (Ω m)	Thickness of layers (m)	Maximum depth of layers (m)	Layer conductivity σ	Fitting error (%)	Layer characteristics	Type curves
		Elevation (m) m.s.l	Latitude ($^{\circ}$ N) Longitude ($^{\circ}$ E)								
7	COLNAS (beside COLPAS)	102.4 m	5° 28. 896 ¹ ° N 7° 32. 398 ¹ ° E	4	$\rho_1 = 250$ $\rho_2 = 1003$ $\rho_3 = 4650$ $\rho_4 = 280.3$	$t_1 = 0.7$ $t_2 = 17.0$ $t_3 = 42.0$	$h_1 = 0.7$ $h_2 = 17.7$ $h_3 = 59.7$	$\sigma_1 = 0.004000$ $\sigma_2 = 0.000997$ $\sigma_3 = 0.000215$ $\sigma_4 = 0.003567$	9	L ₁ = Silts L ₂ = Fine-grained sands L ₃ = Coarse-grained sands (Aquiferous zone) L ₄ = Silts	AK
8	Works Department Junction	113.0 m	5° 28. 766 ¹ ° N 7° 33. 928 ¹ ° E	5	$\rho_1 = 150$ $\rho_2 = 75$ $\rho_3 = 151$ $\rho_4 = 7168$ $\rho_5 = 99000$	$t_1 = 0.8$ $t_2 = 1.5$ $t_3 = 1.0$ $t_4 = 6.0$	$h_1 = 0.8$ $h_2 = 2.3$ $h_3 = 3.3$ $h_4 = 9.3$	$\sigma_1 = 0.006667$ $\sigma_2 = 0.013333$ $\sigma_3 = 0.006623$ $\sigma_4 = 0.000140$ $\sigma_6 = 0.000010$		L ₁ = Silts L ₂ = Clay L ₃ = Silts L ₄ = Sandstone L ₅ = Sandstone (Saturated zone)	HAA
9	CNREM junction	106.7m	5° 28. 589 ¹ ° N 7° 32. 388 ¹ ° E	5	$\rho_1 = 84$ $\rho_2 = 508$ $\rho_3 = 3980$ $\rho_4 = 4190$ $\rho_5 = 5640$	$t_1 = 1.4$ $t_2 = 1.2$ $t_3 = 5.7$ $t_4 = 11.6$	$h_1 = 1.4$ $h_2 = 2.6$ $h_3 = 8.3$ $h_4 = 19.9$	$\sigma_1 = 0.011905$ $\sigma_2 = 0.001969$ $\sigma_3 = 0.000251$ $\sigma_4 = 0.000239$ $\sigma_5 = 0.000177$	10	L ₁ = Clay L ₂ = Fine-grained silty-sands L ₃ = Coarse-grained sands L ₄ = Coarse-grained sands L ₅ = Coarse-grained sands /Sandstone (Saturated zone)	AAA

4. CONCLUSION

It is hereby concluded that despite the shallow depth of investigation used in the assessment of the groundwater potential of the study area; the study has indicated that Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike and its environs have huge sustainable groundwater potential.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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